

Editorial Thanks: IHRJ Completes Three Years of Successful Publication

IHRJ Editorial Team

Dear readers and authors,

It is an immense pleasure to inform you that the current issue is the 36th Issue in the glorious publishing history of IHRJ, and we have completed three years of providing an international global platform to all our authors and readers to publish, read and disseminate scientific knowledge.

The editorial board wishes your safety during these testing times of the COVID-19 Pandemic. We urge you all to follow basic hygiene measures like washing your hands every 20 minutes and sneezing on your closed elbow, etc.

There is no need to panic and do follow WHO and CDC guidelines for the prevention of COVID-19.

Stay safe and educate others regarding their safety to prevent the COVID-19 pandemic.

The entire idea of IHRJ was born when the editor and co-editor decided to provide a platform to the researchers that is quick to answer their queries and be there for researchers at all time. And thus, after brainstorming for a lot of names, International Healthcare Research Journal (IHRJ) was agreed upon.

After this, the main work began. While the co-editor began working on the website design, the editor started to gather a team of dedicated researchers and clinicians to be member of the national and international editorial board. The first issue was released on 12th April, 2017 and we applied for our ISSN number, initiating the series of indexings and constant upgradation of the journal based on the response of our users.

In the span of 36 months, we have covered a lot of ground and our humble achievements are:

1. NLM cataloged journal within 6 months of launch.
2. Shifting from a normal website to OJS 3.0 with a dedicated journal management system for further transparency and convenience of our authors which

is based on global standards.

3. Proudly partnering for the 5th Medical Tourism Annual Conference, held on the 13th and 14th of March 2019 in Zagreb, Croatia.
4. Publications from various countries: Saudi Arabia, Nepal, USA, Ivory Coast, Madagascar, Sudan, Nigeria, Canada, etc.
5. Partial sponsor for the 25th National IAPHD conference held at Modinagar (2018).
6. Plagiarism free manuscripts.
7. DOI number generated for every article.
8. Round the clock support to our authors.
9. HTML, EPUB and MOBI files generated of articles after October 2018.
10. Starting April 2019, the journal website is SSL certified, making it more secure.
11. Inclusion in Index Copernicus, Europub and BASE
12. Submission of all metadata to OAI-PMH, Zenodo, Crossref and Index Copernicus.
13. Welcoming onboard newer reviews and editorial board members
14. A total of 235 manuscripts have been published from April 2017- 31st December, 2019.
15. We have also published a total of 1086 pages of scientific literature.

Future Plans

1. IHRJ aims to visit at least one international conference every year for increasing the reach of the journal.

2. Indexing in various agencies.
3. Hiring more staff to handle the increased flow of manuscripts.

The journey for IHRJ has just started. We thank those who have believed in us for it's because of them that IHRJ has come so far.....

*"No Road is long...
When Dreams are BIG...
And Sky is the limit...."*
-Anonymous

We seek your continued support as we start with our 4th Volume scheduled to be published on or before 25th April, 2020.

With Thanks and Regards,
Editorial Team
International Healthcare Research Journal (IHRJ).